

Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Breast Cancer at the National Cancer Center in Benghazi

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Abstract

Background: Breast cancer ranks among the top five cancers in Libya, with incidence rates varying globally and generally lower in African countries such as Libya and Nigeria. **Aim:** This study aimed to characterize the demographic and clinical profiles of breast cancer patients treated at the Oncology Department of the National Cancer Center in Benghazi, Libya. **Methods:** A retrospective cross-sectional study was conducted at the aforementioned department from February to August 2024. The study included 100 patients. Patients' data were extracted from medical records and analyzed using Microsoft Excel 2016. **Results:** The study patients comprised predominantly Libyan females, with a mean age of 55.4 years. Most patients (98%) were non-smokers, and diabetes was the most frequently reported comorbidity. Nearly half (49%) of patients had no family history of breast cancer. Invasive ductal carcinoma was the predominant tumor type. Surgical treatment was the primary modality, frequently combined with chemotherapy and radiotherapy. **Conclusion:** The breast cancer patient population in this study was mainly female with an average age of 55.4 years. The high prevalence of diabetes underscores potential lifestyle influences on breast cancer risk. The absence of family history in nearly half of the cases emphasizes the importance of broad-based awareness and screening programs.

Keywords: breast cancer, invasive ductal carcinoma, chemotherapy, radiotherapy, recurrence, Benghazi

Introduction

Worldwide, breast cancer accounts for one in four cancer cases and is responsible for six cancer-related deaths among women (Boder et al, 2011). The incidence of breast cancer varies significantly across regions; as Western countries, such as Finland, report higher rates, while African countries like Libya and Nigeria have lower incidences (Boder et al., 2011). Furthermore, breast cancer is often diagnosed at a younger age in African patients compared to their European counterparts (Boder et al., 2011).

In Libya, breast cancer is the most prevalent cancer among women, according to the GLOBOCAN 2020 study (Houssein, 2024). While breast cancer is common in women, particularly those aged 50-69, it is most frequently observed in high-income countries (Zhu et al., 2023). Early diagnosis is crucial for improving survival rates for breast cancer. However, due to its propensity to spread easily, regular screening is essential (Zhu et al., 2023). The number of adults diagnosed with cancer who also have one or more chronic health conditions is steadily increasing. Aging is associated with a higher risk of developing cancer alongside other age-related illnesses such as diabetes, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, heart disease, arthritis, and hypertension (Duthie et al., 2017). A significant majority of older cancer patients, especially those aged 60 and above, live with

additional chronic conditions. Moreover, older adults managing three or more chronic illnesses tend to have nearly three times as many healthcare visits compared to those without chronic conditions (Duthie et al., 2017). As the population of individuals living with both cancer and multiple chronic diseases continues to grow, it becomes increasingly important to gain a deeper understanding of their healthcare experiences and needs (Duthie et al., 2017).

There are two types of tumors: benign tumors, which are not dangerous and can be removed by doctors without usually recurring, and malignant tumors, which are life-threatening and have the ability to spread from one part of the body to another (Zhu et al., 2023). Additionally, one of the major risks associated with malignant cancer is its potential to reappear in patients after treatment and recovery, a phenomenon known as cancer recurrence (Houssein et al., 2024). It has also been reported that breast cancer mortality rates are higher in low socio-economic countries (Fu et al., 2025). Therefore, efforts should prioritize these regions by implementing swift intervention strategies to address and reduce the escalating cancer burden (Fu et al., 2025).

There are different types of breast cancer, with the most common being invasive ductal carcinoma and invasive lobular carcinoma (Elfrgani et al., 2024; Masood et al.,

therapy, either chemotherapy, radiotherapy or hormonal therapy, was not indicated.

In this study, the data analysis indicated also that, within the represented sample, a substantial majority of breast cancer cases (93%) did not have a recurrence. In contrast, a smaller fraction of cases (7%) experienced a recurrence.

Figure 3. Types of therapies applied to breast cancer patients.

Discussion

This study aimed to investigate the demographic and clinical characteristics of breast cancer in patients admitted to the National Cancer Center in Benghazi. The predominance of females in this study aligns with global breast cancer trends and may reflect both biological and social risk factors. Previous studies have reported similar trends regarding the average age of patients (Masood *et al.*, 2025; Elhawari *et al.*, 2025). The average age of 55.4 years for patients diagnosed with breast cancer suggests that many may be experiencing hormonal menopausal changes, which can influence both the development and progression of the disease (Chlebowski and Anderson, 2012; Elfrgani *et al.*, 2024; Masood *et al.*, 2025; Elhawari *et al.*, 2025). This finding is consistent with existing literature that highlights the age-related incidence of breast cancer, although some studies have indicated a lower age of incidence (Elfrgani *et al.*, 2024; Masood *et al.*, 2025). According to the American Cancer Society (2022), the risk of breast cancer increases with age, with the majority of cases diagnosed in women over 50. Furthermore, women diagnosed at older ages may present with different comorbidities that can complicate treatment decisions (Derks *et al.*, 2016).

The current study provides valuable insights into the prevalence of chronic diseases and family history among patients diagnosed with breast cancer. Among those with chronic conditions, 10 patients were diagnosed with diabetes mellitus. The association between diabetes and breast cancer is supported by multiple studies, which suggest that insulin resistance and hyperglycemia may promote tumorigenesis through various pathways, including increased levels of insulin-like growth factors (Chlebowski and Anderson, 2012). Additionally, the presence of other chronic conditions such as hypertension, heart disease, and hypothyroidism complicates the clinical landscape, as patients with hypertension may require careful management during chemotherapy due to potential cardiovascular risks (Pandey *et al.*, 2023). These findings align with existing literature that emphasizes the importance of monitoring

chronic conditions in cancer patients (Pandey *et al.*, 2023). Comorbidities like diabetes and hypertension are prevalent among cancer patients and can adversely affect survival rates, indicating a need for integrated care approaches that address both cancer treatment and the management of chronic diseases (Pandey *et al.*, 2023).

Regarding family history, 24% of reported cases had a close family member affected by the disease. However, the significant proportion of patients without a family history suggests that sporadic cases are common. This result is consistent with findings from other studies indicating that most breast cancers are not hereditary (Patnaik *et al.*, 2011; Haber *et al.*, 2021).

The distribution of cancer involvement across breast sides showed no difference for either the right or left breast, with only 4% of cases being bilateral, which is consistent with previous research (Elfrgani *et al.*, 2024). The size of breast tumors at diagnosis is a well-established prognostic factor. Tumors measuring less than 2 cm are generally associated with a better prognosis compared to larger tumors (Chudgar and Mankoff, 2017). The high percentage of tumors in the 2-5 cm range suggests that a considerable number of patients may present with more advanced disease, which could necessitate more aggressive treatment approaches (Chudgar and Mankoff, 2017). In terms of tumor grade, the findings are in agreement with previous studies, indicating that the majority of patients fell into grade 2, with a smaller number classified as grade 3 (Chlebowski and Anderson, 2012; Elfrgani *et al.*, 2024). Tumor grade is determined by the degree of differentiation of cancer cells and serves as a crucial indicator of tumor aggressiveness. Higher-grade tumors (grade 3) are typically associated with poorer outcomes due to their more aggressive nature and higher likelihood of metastasis. The predominance of grade 2 tumors in this study suggests a potentially favorable prognosis.

Histologically, invasive ductal carcinoma (IDC) was the most prevalent subtype, accounting for 80% of cases in this study. This high incidence of IDC aligns with existing literature, which consistently identifies IDC as the predominant form of breast cancer (Chlebowski and Anderson, 2012; Elfrgani *et al.*, 2024). The current study also provides insights into treatment modalities, revealing a predominant reliance on surgical interventions, specifically mastectomy and modified radical mastectomy (MRM). Surgical removal of cancerous tissue is a cornerstone of breast cancer treatment (Ozmen and Ozmen, 2023), with the data indicating that mastectomy was performed in 10 cases and MRM in 7 cases. Mastectomy, which involves the complete removal of one or both breasts, is often indicated in cases of large tumors or multifocal disease (Ozmen and Ozmen, 2023). MRM, which preserves some breast tissue while removing lymph nodes, is frequently employed for patients with node-positive disease and has been shown to provide effective local control (Ozmen and Ozmen, 2023). Additionally, the study highlights that chemotherapy was the primary adjuvant therapy administered either alone, in 33% of cases, or in combination with radiotherapy in 35% of cases. The combination of chemotherapy with radiotherapy is often recommended for patients

undergoing breast-conserving surgery to minimize local recurrence rates (Wang and Wu, 2023). The findings presented indicate that a substantial majority of patients did not experience a recurrence following treatment. This aligns with established literature suggesting that effective surgical and adjuvant therapies can lead to favorable long-term outcomes of treatment for breast cancer patients (EBCTCG, 2018).

Conclusion

The patient population in this study shows a significant representation from Libya, with the majority diagnosed with invasive ductal carcinoma. Surgical intervention was the primary treatment modality, often supplemented by chemotherapy and radiotherapy. Notably, nearly half of the participants lacked a family history of breast cancer, highlighting the critical need for screening and awareness programs. These initiatives should be extended to individuals without a family history, considering the high proportion of sporadic cases.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Authors' contribution

All authors contributed to the study conception and design. Material preparation and data collection were performed by Wail A. Elhawari, Tareq E. Lehmidi, Retaj A. Salem, Nabila M. Alwarfali, Sondos F. Alsadeg, Aisha M. Bazama, and Malak A. Alrayani. Data analysis was performed by Abeer H. Amer. The first draft of the manuscript was written by Hend R. Awad. All authors commented on the manuscript versions and read and approved the final version.

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